

THE POLITICAL ROLE OF WATER IN CENTRAL ASIA: THE CASE OF THE AMUDARYA AND SYRDARYA RIVERS

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Annotation: This research paper examines the up-to-date geopolitical zone of Central Asia, the Syrdarya and Amudarya rivers are the vital resources that ensure the region's peace, political and economic survival. The disintegration of the Soviet Union demolished the old water management system and it led to conflicts between upstream countries that focused on producing electricity and downstream countries that focused on agriculture. While water management remains firsthand source of regional strain due to diverging national interests, the intensifying climate crisis and the rise of new geopolitical challenges, such as Afghanistan's Qoshtepa Canal project are now the crucial determinants forcing upstream and downstream countries to abandon water resource sovereignty approach. The creation of unified regional system is the only viable approach to guarantee long-lasting term of peace and economic stability in Central Asia.

Key words: Water management, geopolitics, power generation, water scarcity, international relations, hydrological system, upstream and downstream states.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqola Markaziy Osiyoning zamonaviy geosiyosiy holatini tahlil qiladi. Amudaryo va Sirdaryo daryolari mintaqaning tinchligi va siyosiy, iqtisodiy barqarorligini ta'minlaydigan hayotiy resurslar hisoblanadi. O'rta Osiyo hududida Sovet Ittifoqining parchalanishi avvalgi suv boshqaruvi tizimini izdan chiqardi va bu yuqori oqimdagi davlatlar hamda quyi oqimdagi davlatlar o'rtasida o'zaro qarama-qarshiliklarga sabab bo'ldi. Yuqori oqimdagi davlatlar asosan elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqarishga e'tibor qaratgan bo'lsa, quyi oqimdagi davlatlar qishloq xo'jaligiga iqtisoslashtirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Suv boshqaruvi, geosiyosat, elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqarish, suv tanqisligi, xalqaro munosabatlar, gidrologik tizim, yuqori va quyi oqim davlatlari.

Introduction

To start, the historical challenge over the water and energy relationship has been a critical element shaping the sophisticated hydro and geopolitical associations between downstream and upstream states in Central Asia. The management of shared water resources has always been one of the significant issues for economic and political stability in the region. This dilemma is mainly based on a situation where upstream countries, particularly Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan that see water as a essential source of energy also electricity production. Since they do not have adequate gas and oil, they keep water in mountain reservoirs during the summer to enable hydroelectric power generation in other seasons of year. However, the downstream countries face an absolutely different situation. Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan are situated on flat plains, these regions experience extremely hot and dry summer conditions. These countries' economic system mostly built on agriculture, especially the production silk and cotton. These

products requires a huge amount of water for irrigation. In these downstream states, the water is highly valuable during the summer and spring seasons. If the upstream states hold the water in reservoirs during the summer to save it for winter electricity production, the farmers of downstream countries will not have enough water for agricultural activities.

.Main part

Tensions arising from water distribution leads to significant economic issues and brings shortages in food availability. Furthermore, this friction has significantly deteriorated since the disintegration of the Soviet Union. Previously, there was a central political governing system in Moscow that regulated upstream countries to share water properly. This system was based on simple economic exchange: the upstream countries Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan provided water for downstream states Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan. In exchange, downstream countries provided upstream states with oil and gas. This political and economical plan managed by one leader, ensuring both food availability and energy production for everyone in Central Asia. Moreover, when countries in Central Asia became independent, this exchange system or “barter” stopped working almost promptly. Each new states started regulating its own national security and economy over the needs of its neighbors. This change in political relationships is usually called “water nationalism”. Since there is no longer a centralized system in water management, the states have separate rules, diverse aims and lack of laws about hydro politics. For instance, the Syrdarya is extensively used for agriculture in the crowded Fergana Valley, while the Amudarya is essential for survival in the regions like Khorezm, Karakalpakstan and Turkmenistan. When upstream state constructs a large new water reservoir on Amudarya or Syrdarya to enhance energy and electricity production for its own national interests, downstream countries become seriously concerned. They have a trepidation about scarcity of water, negative effects to population, livestock, industries and agriculture. The history of water relations in Central Asia was fraught with acute struggle for water that was always the most vital resource in such arid intercontinental region located far from seas and oceans.

Moving to the next significant challenge, the construction of the Qoshtepa Canal in Afghanistan is a new and major aspect for Central Asia. How do the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers influence political relations between Central Asian countries? For a prolonged period, only the five states of Central Asia claimed about the main water sources: Amudarya and Syrdarya. Nevertheless, Afghanistan has recently started showing interest in Amudarya and Syrdarya. The canal project called “Qoshtepa” has started by Afghanistan to control the river Amudarya. Afghanistan now started a giant project to build a 285-kilometer canal in northern side of its own territory. Qoshtepa canal will take a enormous quantity of water from Amudarya. The aim of this project is to help Afghan farmers and develop agriculture of this nation. Since, Afghanistan did not participated in old agreements with Central Asian states, this giant project leads to numerous issues and uncertainty. For that reason, downstream countries like Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan are deeply concerned that these countries could lose as much as 15% or 20% of their water supply once the canal is completed. According to the World Resources Institute, Uzbekistan, alongside Afghanistan and Turkmenistan, is categorized as a country facing “high” water stress. In Uzbekistan, a staggering 90% of its available water resources are allocated to agriculture, a sector that contributed 28% to the country’s GDP as of 2019. There is also concern that the launch of the canal will increase soil salinization, and that

further implementation of the agro-industrial complex by Afghans will spoil large areas of land and increase the amount of salt water in the lower reaches of the Amudarya.

In addition, to the scarcity of water, this situation changes the economical and political stability of the entire nations. In former times, Afghanistan was relatively inactive in using the water of Amudarya due to several years of war. However, in the present situation, Afghanistan wants to use its legislation to the water in order to enhance its own economy and food availability. This means that the management and distribution of Amudarya and Syrdarya not only between Central Asian states, but also Afghanistan too. This situation is a highly challenging because if there is no legal and official agreement with Afghanistan, the water levels in the lower parts of the Amudarya will decrease more and more, making life harder for hundreds of millions of people.

Apart from that, the Qoshtepa canal is being built at high speed by outdated technologies and many experts showing worry for that. If the canal is not constructed accurately, a huge amount of water might sink into the ground. This can lead to massive waste of water of Amudarya. Consequently, this would be a significant issue for every nation in Central Asia because the Amudarya is already dealing with water scarcity. Since the Amudarya is already losing its volume because of melting glaciers and climate change, this type of inaccuracy could lead to absolute disappearance of what remains of the Aral Sea ecosystem.

Therefore, this new political reality makes water management more threatening than early times. If each state continues to act without cooperation, the competition for the remaining water will lead to potential border issues. The Qoshtepa Canal project is an obvious sign of old and outdated managing system of water. To avoid a significant regional crisis, it is vital for all states in Central Asia including Afghanistan. All regions should establish a new, contemporary and participatory framework for mutual assistance. This should include not only unbiased distribution of water resources but also shared responsibility for financing better and more modern infrastructure and implementing advantageous technologies, such as drip irrigation systems. Without such collaborative action, the canal risks evolving from an advancement program into a long-lasting source of regional instability.

Apart from the technical and political issues, the increasing climate crisis is the most destabilizing long-term threat to the water management of the Amudarya and Syrdarya basins. Over a long period of time, people claimed that mountain glaciers would not melt and that water supplies would never run out. However, scientific data shows that the glaciers in the Pamir and Tian Shan mountains are melting rapidly due to rising global temperatures. Scientists predict that if this situation continues without stopping, this may lead to serious issues in Central Asia. For instance, the region could lose a tremendous part of its glacier volume by 2050. This means that while there might be more water and even floods in the short term. But after that, the total amount of water in the rivers will decrease dramatically in the near future, leaving millions of people in a chronic drought condition.

In addition to melting of glaciers, weather patterns across Central Asia are becoming increasingly dramatic and intense. The region is experiencing extended summers and considerably lower precipitation levels, which worsens the pressure on the stressed Amudarya and Syrdarya basins. With decreasing river volumes, the levels of agricultural chemicals and salt become more concentrated, making the water unsafe to use and drink. For example, in

Kyrgyzstan, 122,800 people were affected by water-related diseases. In Turkmenistan, inhabitants affected by typhoid, intestinal infections and virus hepatitis. In Uzbekistan, agricultural productivity reduced dramatically and led to several diseases, such as tuberculosis, kidney, respiratory diseases, liver, cancer and anemia. The situation worsened during 2001-2002 in Karakalpakstan and Khorezm from a drought period and scarcity of water negatively impacted hygiene of people. This environmental deterioration generates a vicious cycle: as soils become more saline, farmers in agriculture forced to use additional water to flush out the salt. This issue creates another major problem that less amount of water would be available for downstream countries. Particularly, this issue is obvious in the Aral Sea region, where the environmental catastrophe has already destroyed local fishing industries and severely impacted the health of millions of people.

This ecological situation mainly shows that state-centered water control is no longer efficient or sustainable strategy for any state in Central Asia. In the past decades, countries were usually able to dispute water allocation without immediate ecological consequences. However, the current climate reality is radically different. The accelerating climate crisis has become a borderless and shared that can affect all nations equally, regardless of their geopolitical or economic position.

Under these circumstances, neither upstream nor downstream countries are able to overcome the significant issues associated with decreasing crystal clear water and shrinking rivers. Single-state policies over water management only deepens mistrust and intensify competition, further destabilizing regional diplomatic relations. Consequently, the need for a collaborated and systematized regional response has shifted from diplomatic recommendation to an essential necessity for survival and long-term stability.

As a result, preventing a complete environmental and economic collapse requires sustained collaboration between countries. This involves establishing a shared regional monitoring system to precisely measure water levels and cooperate in shared investment in efficient water technologies across national boundaries. For instance, replacing outdated irrigation techniques with drip irrigation could conserve enough water to compensate for losses caused by climate change. This third challenge highlights that the future of Central Asia mostly depends on whether these countries choose diplomatic and peaceful relationships rather than conflict over water management. If they succeed in managing Amudarya and Syrdarya being collaborative as a unified ecosystem, they can turn a potential crisis into a chance for regional integration, peace and economic stability.

In addition to water diplomacy, the modernization of infrastructure is vital, even though supporters of national sovereignty argue that in internalized needs must be the priority. Upstream nations and Afghanistan maintain that they have the right to use water for their own energy and food availability without external interference. However, the present condition of widespread water waste makes this a narrowly nationalist approach is harmful to every state. The majority of water is lost in past years, through leaking canals before reaching agricultural fields. Consequently, the most effective solution is to progress toward a “green economy” by investing in solar energy and drip irrigation. By using technology instead of making conflict over Amudarya and Syrdarya, countries of Central Asia can share resources more fairly, peacefully. Eventually, choosing contemporary collaboration over outdated disputes is the only strategy to protect the region from a permanent water crisis and scarcity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the shared management of Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers represents the most essential factor for the long-lasting stability and survival of Central Asian states. The progression from a concentrated Soviet political system to “water nationalism” has created significant issue that now deepened by the construction of the Qoshtepa canal and the alarming glacier loss in mountainous regions. While individual nations often prioritize their own energy and agricultural running system, the looming threat of a permanent state of drought proves that isolationist political strategies are no longer viable. For the region to prosper, it is vital to shift toward “hydro-solidarity” through the adoption of modern irrigation technologies and inclusive regional treaties. In the final analysis, the future of Central Asia depends on these nations’ capacity to turn water from a driver of conflict into a basis for shared environmental and economic resilience.

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